

DEVELOPMENT AND POPULARIZATION OF METHODS OF TEACHING STUDENTS OF THE DIRECTION OF FINE ARTS THROUGH INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY

M.A.Ubaydullayev

Namangan davlat universiteti

“San’atshunoslik” fakulteti o’qituvchisi

maxmudjon.ubaydullayev6860@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The article focuses on the management of innovative activities in the higher education system with information technology. These changes are based on the strategic direction of higher education institutions and the active implementation of innovative activities. Keywords: higher education system, intensive, information and Communication Technology, Innovation, Strategy, computer technology.

Introduction. in the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 21, 2020 PQ-4688 " to restore our national heritage in the fields of fine and Applied Arts, to fully convey to our people the rich creative heritage of Kamoliddin Bekhzad, to perpetuate the memory of outstanding artists and folk masters who have made a significant contribution to the development in order to further increase the efficiency of the design industry in ofham," it was determined to carry out large-scale work in three points, to ensure its implementation. Discussion and results. Preparation of modern textbooks, teaching and methodological manuals and materials, stimulation of pedagogical personnel and talented students.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS: To increase the artistic and spiritual level of works of fine and applied art, to further develop the activities of exhibitions, to strengthen the material support of the Academy of Arts. The implementation of tasks in the main areas, such as training and professional development of personnel in the fields of fine and applied art and design, was determined by the deadline. At the same time, the upbringing of potential specialists of systemic development does not give the expected result. ¹Basically, the relevance of the topic lies in the fact that today the usual traditional methods of literature and teaching methods seem ineffective. Thanks to the attention of the head of state to art, we have a number of shortcomings in providing mature personnel, although new modern directions have been opened in higher educational institutions. Baratarafing such shortcomings requires pedagogical staff to improve their quality and competitive tolerance. In teaching students of the direction of Fine Arts of Higher Education, distance and traditional methods of education can be used, at the same time, in practice. For this, of course, it will be advisable to take into account the opinion of the professors and students. The daily load of students will need to

¹ Baymetov, B. B., & Sharipjonov, M. S. O. (2020). Development Of Students' Descriptive Competencies In Pencil Drawing Practice. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 2(08), 261-267

study and analyze the indicator of mastering the specialty and humanities during two or three pairs of lessons. The COVID19 pandemic, which brought heavy calamity to humanity as a plague of the century, also caused some sectors to develop in a forced way. Basically, in the virtual world, its own intermediate communication, lesson sessions or similar processes have been developed and formed. The distance Organization of classes in higher education has formed qualifications and skills in students, professor teachers. From practice in this process, it began to be seen that new ideas could be applied. In the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan of April 21, 2020, the activities of certain fronts, neglected due to attention to fine arts, were newly formed. This decision was made on time. (1) Barreda Ramirez cited in her science that it is necessary for a student and professor teacher to achieve effective results in distance education in two areas. The distance Organization of classes in higher education has formed qualifications and skills in students, professor teachers. From practice in this process, it began to be seen that new ideas could be applied. In the decree of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan of April 21, 2020, the activities of certain fronts, neglected due to attention to fine arts, were newly formed. This decision was made on time. (1) Barreda Ramirez cited in her science that it is necessary for a student and professor teacher to achieve effective results in distance education in two areas. (2) The article reveals the essence and content of various concepts of artistic training developed in the Russian Federation from history. Describes the difference in approaches to teaching Fine Arts in the² theory of various concepts. (3) the application of ICT in the teaching of Fine Arts and its achievements are presented in Haik and in modern art with the application of ICT, the student's scientific views on the development of skills and skills are presented. (4) the processes of encircling higher education with ICT have been carried out. This process is increasing in the percenta³ge sc⁴ore. It is aimed at expanding the possibilities of working in the virtual world and ⁵achieving the result in the areas of Education. A proposal for new innovative ideas was adopted and a proposal was made to introduce. Application of the effect of the organization of distance and traditional lessons positive results keltrishi was disclosed. The goal was to increase the level of knowledge in students in this rapidly developing process, which brought wider opportunities. The practical part of the lesson exercises is in the audience, the lecture parts organization from such types as distance chat training, Web training, teleconference lead to a greater result. At the rapid stages of development, students also adapted to the Times, and their attention requires a lot of skill from the professor teacher. That is why the involvement of the student's main useful work capacity in the practical part increases the chances of achieving the goal with his physical strength. The fact that coursework is more formed in the visual arts with its practical part forms the basis for

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⁴ Formation of Ancient Sculpture on the Territory of Uzbekistan Dilmurod Saymamutovich Pulatov Candidate of Arts, Namangan State University, Uzbekistan Email: dilmurodpulatov658@gmail.com <http://dx.doi.org/10.47814/ijssrr.v5i7.481>

⁵ Amanullaev, A. A. (2022). CURRENT ISSUES IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE TEACHERS OF FINE ARTS. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW* ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor

achieving the same goal. In lecture sessions, however, this J arayon gives the student the ability to work independently in an internet system. In particular, the creator presented on the topic will have the opportunity to see his works in virtual museums and analyze it. With this, the activities of virtual libraries will also develop a revitalized data exchange. For example, if we analyze the possibility of using the student's agenda by nature, a person will endure active mental work from dawn to the first half of the day. At this time, the lesson will be targeted if we organize a remote part of the lecture based on the nature and complexity of our training. The use of a science test, a set of golsary questions and an educational methodology in general is convenient in virtual lesson sessions. The time of arrival at a higher educational institution is 11:30, and by this time the student will not be able to communicate with the students in the audience if lecture classes are organized from 7:00 or 7:30 in the morning his opinion was prevented from being distracted. The method of conducting practical classes as a team at the university provides students with the opportun⁶ity to analyze th⁷eir shortcomings and achievements by observing other students 'class work.

Conclusion: Practical classes in teaching students of the direction of Fine Arts require an above-ground head characteristic of workshop training. And it is possible that in lectures the usual environment does not fit. The main part of the pairs in the lesson schedule passes until the student arrives at the OTM. Assessment is also introduced in the system based on the characteristics of various disciplines. In the visual arts, the assessment mechanism was generally found to be optimal not divided into points, but because the relative assessment mechanism resulted in a more useful result. The introduction of this mechanism into practice serves as an opportunity for students to master the disciplines of the specialty in depth. Enrichment of bujarayon with the method of Education brings an effective result.

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